

Parameter identification in wind turbine control

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Abstract

Smart and robust control strategies are key to exploit wind energy efficiently. Accordingly, the study group was aimed towards developing a procedure (using parameter identification techniques) for the design of a set of control parameters able to lead a wind turbine to track a prescribed dynamics. In order to carry out a proof-of-concept of the developed procedure, two models are built. Firstly, a detailed model of a heavily-studied 5 MW wind turbine proposed by NREL is built using OpenFAST software. Solutions from this model (using a known control strategy) under some particular (an relevant) wind conditions are used to compute a prescribed wind-turbine behaviour used as a reference dynamics. Then, a simplified SIMULINK model is built. In this second model, control parameters and, in some cases, several mechanical/electrical parameters are considered unknown. Finally, using the solution from the first model as the reference dynamics, the identification problem involving missing mechanical/electrical wind-turbine parameters and/or control parameters in the simplified model is tackled. The developed tools provide a suitable platform to test efficient identification techniques to be used later in a (real) industrial framework.

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1. Introduction

Wind energy is one of the fastest growing renewable energy sources in the recent years with the World Wind Energy Association reporting 597GW of installed capacities in 2018 while growing around 10% year-on-year. The EU alone has a net total of 189GW of installed wind power, more than any other form of energy generation. The most valuable tool in exploiting this energy resource is the *wind turbine* – a complex dynamical system designed to extract the energy in the wind in fluctuating and erratic environmental conditions while being subjected to variable demands in the connected electric grid. The efficiency and reliability of a wind turbine is dependent on its installed location - either onshore or offshore, along-with environmental conditions like temperature, humidity, possibility of ice-formation and precipitation. It is also strongly dependent on the control system which decides the response of the system to changing wind speed and directions, grid voltage drops, regulation of voltage and frequency in generated power among others.

Figure 1: Power Curve for Wind Energy extraction [3]

One of the main technological challenges for a given wind turbine is maximization of efficiency over different operational conditions. Achieving high efficiency requires optimum and robust control strategies as is demonstrated in the power curve shown in Figure 1.

A multi-disciplinary engineering firm, *Solute* (based in Madrid, Spain) which provides technical and consulting services in the wind energy sector, posed a relevant problem at the 147 ESGI towards attaining a robust approach for parameter identification in an operational wind turbine control. The following sections report the methodology followed by the study group towards

that goal.

2. Elements of a wind turbine

Figure 2: Parts of a Wind Turbine

A typical offshore horizontal axis wind turbine which is of focus in this study has various parts as shown in Figure 2. It is physically made of three basic parts: the rotor blades, the nacelle and the tower. The rotor blades are the easily identifiable parts of the turbine which are specifically designed to convert aerodynamic loads into rotational energy which drives a shaft. The nacelle is a strong, hollow shell consisting of the main machinery – the electric generation unit made of the main drive shaft, a generator and a gearbox among others. It also contains the blade pitch control unit, a hydraulic system which controls the blade angles for optimum energy extraction and the yaw drive which controls the turbine orientation relative to the wind direction. The tower is made generally of a strong metal frame capable of handling the load of the rotor blades and the heavy nacelle. The structure is firmly held in place with a foundation and also consists of utility systems connecting it to the electric grid.

3. Control design

Variable-speed wind turbine generators can operate at a certain range of rotor speeds. This is achieved through the implementation of blade-pitch control and generator electrical torque control. The degree of speed variation in these machines is closely related to the type of generator they use: from dual-speed

generators with pole switching to doubly fed induction generators (DFIG) for a moderate range of variable speed and direct-drive (DD) systems for a wide range of variable speed.

In figure 1 a schematic representation of a generic power curve for a variable-speed and pitch-controlled wind turbine generator was shown.

Three important regions were indicated in that figure (a fourth region, only sketched in the plot, corresponds to high values of the wind speed where almost no power extraction takes place due to safety concerns). According to the power supplied to the grid (incoming wind power minus losses), the graph can be split into two main areas: the area identified as *below rated power* and the area marked *above rated power*.

Below rated power (this is, below rated wind speed) the wind turbine generator produces only a fraction of its total design power. Therefore, the control system performs an optimization strategy to capture the maximum amount of energy at every wind speed. On the other hand, above rated power (this is, above rated wind speed) the control has to perform a limitation strategy to generate only the rated power.

Regarding blade-pitch and generator torque control, the three regions of the power curve present the following characteristics:

- Region 1

Commonly known as the torque control region, where wind speeds are low. It starts when wind speed is above the wind turbine design cut-in value, V_{cut-in} . The objective of the control system in this region is to obtain the maximum aerodynamic efficiency.

The power coefficient of a wind turbine, c_p , is a function of the tip speed ratio λ and blade-pitch angle θ . Therefore, maximum aerodynamic efficiency will be achieved by means of manipulating the generator electrical torque in order to get a particular and pre-fixed ratio (optimum tip speed ratio, λ_{opt}) between wind speed and rotor speed. At the same time, the blade-pitch control system will keep the angle in its optimum value for power production θ_{opt} .

- Region 2

This region is usually called the transition region, characterised by medium wind speeds. In this region it is not possible to obtain the desired tip speed ratio because the rotor speed is near to its maximum value (which happens when wind speed reaches the characteristic value V_{Ω}). The generator electric torque has to be increased until the turbine reaches its rated power. This is usually done by following a high slope generator electric torque/rotor-speed reference or by implementing a closed-loop proportional-integral (PI) controller.

Blade-pitch control will typically keep the pitch angle constant and set to its optimum value along this region of the power curve, as seen in region 1.

- Region 3

This is the blade–pitch control region, which corresponds to high wind speeds. The blades have to move the pitch angle in order to limit the incoming power, therefore controlling the rotor wind speed and minimizing the mechanical loads at the same time. This is typically done by implementing a closed – loop PI controller which generates a pitch rate control signal to send to the actuators using error in rotor speed (w.r.t. to its rated value) as an input. Gain scheduling techniques are also used to compensate for the effect on power sensitivity with respect to pitch angle (this is the derivative of the aerodynamic power extracted from the incoming air by the rotor with respect to the blade – pitch angle) which can vary significantly with wind speed and current blade-pitch angle for many rotor designs. In addition to ensure the operation of the machine in rated conditions, the blade-pitch control system can contribute to an important cost reduction and life–operating augmentation if load attenuation is targeted as a primary objective when designing the controller or if a blade-independent control strategy to reduce loads is performed. In this region of the power curve, generator torque control will work to try to keep either generated power or electric torque at their rated value (depending on the strategy chosen by the control design engineer) due to the fact that rotor (and therefore drivetrain) speed is being controlled by the blade – pitch control system.

4. A roadmap towards control design

The statement of the (real) industrial problem can be written as follows: *For a particular wind turbine subject to some (temporal) wind pattern a reference behaviour of the time–dependent rotor speed is prescribed. Parameters of a PI control strategy are then searched so that evolution of a (detailed) turbine model (under the proposed control strategy) is able to track the reference behaviour.*

Of course, this problem involves many ingredients that are completely out of the scope of the present study. Firstly, a very detailed wind turbine model is needed since the identification of the control strategy is made using this model (and not the real wind turbine). Secondly, a real control strategy must consider not only several control regions (as explained above) but also a number of additional variables that must be taken into account in the design of the control. Both aspects lead to a complicated formulation of the identification problem to be tackled.

Keeping in mind this *final* identification problem, a simplified version will be considered here. This (more simple) problem is intended to retain the essential ingredients of the original one but will be easier to formulate in order to provide a workbench to test different ideas. In this simplified problem,

a realistic enough wind turbine model is considered and a rotor speed time series (corresponding to a wind speed time series and a particular set of PI control parameters) is generated. This rotor speed is taken as a *proxy* for the desired wind turbine rotor speed and used as a reference solution in the parameter identification problem. Then, a simplified wind turbine model is generated and PI controller parameters needed to reproduce the reference solution are identified. It must be noted that some aerodynamical, mechanical or electrical parameters in this simplified model may need to be identified from observations of the realistic model behaviour. This is also the case in real industrial problem, where some wind turbine details could be unknown to the controller designer. Solving parameter identification problems in this case is expected to provide valuable guidelines to solve the (real) industrial control design problem described above.

In order to prepare the (simplified) framework to test control design ideas, a number of tools are needed:

- A reference wind turbine needs to be considered. It was decided that a well documented 5MW reference wind turbine developed by National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL, <https://www.nrel.gov>) was to be used. This model will be described in section 5.
- A tool to build a detailed model for the reference wind turbine. After considering several available alternatives, the open source software OpenFAST (also developed by National Renewable Energy Laboratory, <https://nwtc.nrel.gov/OpenFAST>) emerges as the best candidate. In particular, a model for the 5MW reference wind turbine is already available. Both the main features of the code and the wind turbine model are described also in section 5.
- A tool to easily develop simple wind turbine models. Among other candidates, SIMULINK (<https://www.mathworks.com/products/simulink>), a graphical programming environment for modelling dynamical systems, providing a number of customizable blocks and developed by MathWorks, was considered a good choice. Implementation of a simplified wind turbine model in SIMULINK is described in section 6.
- A toolbox of parameter identification techniques able to easily interact with the previous modelling tools. The selected toolbox is AMIGO2 (available at <https://sites.google.com/site/amigo2toolbox>), developed by the (Bio)Process Engineering group at IIM-CSIC. Both the relevant aspects of such a toolbox and its capabilities can be found in section 7

5. NREL reference 5MW wind turbine and OpenFAST software

The 5MW reference wind turbine was developed by National Renewable Energy Laboratory(NREL) with an aim of assimilating the various concept studies assessing offshore wind technology. It developed detailed specifications of a representative utility-scale 5MW wind turbine now known as the *NREL offshore 5-MW baseline wind turbine*. The baseline wind turbine is a conventional three-bladed upwind model turbine with variable-speed, variable blade-pitch-to-feather-control. The model was a result of collection of design information obtained from various turbine manufacturers along with publicly available properties from conceptual models in the earlier WindPACT, RECOFF, and DOWEC projects sponsored by the US and Dutch governments. NREL published a detailed report ([4]) documenting the specifications of the offshore 5-MW baseline wind turbine model — including the aerodynamic, structural, and control-system properties together with the rationale behind its development. The model has since been used as the *de-facto* reference by research teams throughout the world to standardize baseline offshore wind turbine specifications and to quantify the benefits of advanced land and sea-based wind energy technologies. Much more detailed specifications of the baseline model may be obtained from [4].

Figure 3: OpenFAST Modules

OpenFAST is an open-source wind turbine simulation tool developed by NREL. As shown in figure 3, the software is organized around three main modules. OpenFAST puts together entirely the NREL baseline wind turbine specifications, and provides *fatigue*, *aerodynamics*, *structures*, and *turbulence* (FAST) models to compute the dynamic response of conventional horizontal-axis wind turbines. It includes a combined modal and multi-body dynamical formulation—demarcating earth, foundation, nacelle, armature, gears, hub tail, and structure furling with the rotor as rigid bodies and tower, blades and driveshafts as flexible bodies. The software provides a non-linear coupling of various physics models like aerodynamics, hydrodynamics (for offshore structures),

control and electrical system dynamics enabling analyses and detailed output on the different responses of a wind turbine. A short presentation of OpenFAST capabilities can be found in [6] and some software documentation is available at <https://openfast.readthedocs.io>.

Figure 4: Simulated control output using OpenFAST

In figure 4 an example with a simulation of the NREL 5MW wind turbine is shown. In the left plot, wind speed (in blue) and rotor speed (in red) for a given choice of the PI controller parameters are represented. In the right plot, rotor speed (red) and blade pitch angle (blue) are plotted. As clearly shown in the figure a low-pass filter is applied in this (realistic) model. This filter will be also considered in the simplified model to be built.

6. A simplified SIMULINK model

The simplified SIMULINK model for the NREL 5MW wind turbine will consist of four main submodels:

- a wind turbine aerodynamics model, determining the mechanical torque and containing a (very) simplified aerodynamics
- a (very simple) gearbox model, incorporating the gear ratio
- a generator model, including information from rotor and generator inertia as well as from electrical circuit parameters
- a PI controller model, incorporating PI control parameters as well as control constraints

The decomposition of the global SIMULINK model in modules is shown in figure 5. In turn, an overview of this global model for the NREL 5MW wind turbine is represented in figure 6. Apart from the four submodels, both a (first order) low pass filter and an aerodynamic efficiency have been added to the model. Remark that, as expected, the only input in the global model is the wind speed.

Each of the four submodels previously listed is (briefly) described below.

Figure 5: SIMULINK global model modules

Figure 6: SIMULINK global model for the NREL reference 5 MW wind turbine

6.1. Wind turbine aerodynamics model

Wind turbine blades transform kinetic energy of the wind into mechanical energy in the form of a torque. Blades aerodynamics is modelled through the power coefficient c_p , that represents the ratio between extracted mechanical power (P_m) and available wind power

$$c_p = \frac{\text{actual extracted power}}{\text{available wind power}} = \frac{P_m}{\frac{1}{2}\rho AU_\infty^3} \quad (1)$$

where ρ represents air density (assumed to be constant), A stands for the surface of the so-called actuator disk (transversal area covered by blades during rotation) and U_∞ is the wind velocity. Betz limit establishes an upper bound for the power coefficient ($c_p^{max} = 16/27$, i.e. around 59%).

In our model, a semiempirical formula for the computation of the power coefficient c_p as a function of blade-pitch angle (θ) and tip-speed ratio (λ , defined as the ratio between tip-speed and wind velocity) is used. More details concerning this simplified aerodynamics modelling can be found in [3]. Using the formula for c_p , the wind speed and the rotor speed at each time during the simulation (in practice, at each time-step during SIMULINK simulation),

this submodel gives as an output the aerodynamic torque acting on the wind turbine rotor.

SIMULINK wind turbine aerodynamics model is shown in figure 7, where parameters in the semiempirical formula

$$c_p(\theta, \lambda) = C_1 (C_2 \alpha_i(\theta, \lambda) - C_3 \theta - C_4) e^{-C_5 \alpha_i(\theta, \lambda)} + C_6 \lambda \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha_i(\theta, \lambda) = \frac{1}{\lambda + C_1' \theta} - \frac{C_2'}{1 + \theta^3} \quad (3)$$

as well as input variables (wind speed, wind turbine rotation velocity, and pitch angle) are observed.

Figure 7: SIMULINK wind turbine aerodynamics model

Moreover, mechanical power produced by the wind turbine (P_m) is converted to rotation torque (T_r) through the rotor speed (ω_r):

$$T_r = \frac{P_m}{\omega_r} \quad (4)$$

6.2. Gearbox model

In large wind turbines, the rotor speed is not adequate to achieve the optimum rotation speed of the electrical generator, so a gearbox is used to increase it. Gears maintain the power transmitted to the generator (excluding friction losses), modifying the torque value and speed by means of a proportionality

constant known as gear ratio G_r . The (very simple) SIMULINK model for the gearbox only includes the gear ratio to convert rotation speed and torque between rotor (or low speed side) and generator (high speed side). The model is represented in figure 8.

Figure 8: SIMULINK gearbox model

6.3. Generator model

The generator is the component in charge of converting the mechanical energy absorbed in the rotor into electrical energy. Doubly-fed induction generator (DFIG) are used in real cases where high-powered wind turbines are involved. In addition, in order for the system to be connected to the grid, it is necessary to adjust the frequency and phase of the AC signal. However, to simplify the problem, a permanent magnet DC generator is considered here.

In this model both the generator (mechanical) dynamics and the electrical circuit for the generator are considered. Concerning the dynamics of the generator, the following model is considered

$$I_r \frac{d\omega_r}{dt} + I_g \frac{d\omega_g}{dt} = T_r - T_{em} - T_{los} \quad (5)$$

where I_r and I_g represent rotor and generator inertia, ω_r and ω_g are rotor and generator rotational velocities, T_r is the mechanical torque (computed from c_p and rotation velocity, as described above), T_{em} stands for the electromagnetic torque (depending on the energy pumped through the electrical circuit) and T_{los} for friction and magnetic losses. Of course, using the gear ratio G_r this equation can be rewritten as

$$(I_r G_r + I_g) \frac{d\omega_g}{dt} = T_r - T_{em} - T_{los} \quad (6)$$

Moreover, a very simple model will be used to determine friction and magnetic losses in T_{los} . Namely, T_{los} will be computed as

$$T_{los} = T_f + B\omega_g \quad (7)$$

Figure 9: SIMULINK generator model

where friction losses, T_f , are assumed to be known in the model.

In some cases, if the power extracted from the wind turbine is known, the value of T_{em} in this model will be given. In other cases, the equivalent load in the electric circuit is known but the circuit itself must be solved in order to obtain T_{em} .

In the second case, we can model $T_{em} = \kappa I_a$ with current I_a being the solution (from Kirchoff's law) of the generator equivalent circuit

$$\kappa\omega_g = L_a \frac{dI_a}{dt} + R_a I_a + R_{load} I_a \quad (8)$$

where $\kappa\omega_g$ is the electromotive force in the generator, R_a and L_a represent parameters of the equivalent circuit and R_{load} represents resistance of the electrical load.

Both models (generator mechanical and electrical models) are represented in figure 9.

6.4. PI controller model

In this case, a standard SIMULINK PID controller block is used in order to compute a target pitch θ_{PI} from the error between rated rotor speed ω_r^{ref} and actual rotor speed ω_r .

$$\theta_{PI} = K_P(\omega_r - \omega_r^{ref}) + K_I \int_0^t (\omega_r(\tau) - \omega_r^{ref}) d\tau \quad (9)$$

In addition, two standard SIMULINK limiter blocks are used to implement limitations on pitch angles (between 0 and $\pi/2$) and pitch rates. As previously mentioned, no pitch actuator is included in this simplified SIMULINK model. The PI controller SIMULINK block is represented in figure 10.

Figure 10: SIMULINK PI controller model

7. Parameter identification

Formally, parameter identification techniques can be indeed reduced to the solution of an optimization problem for an objective function measuring the misfitting between the model solution (for some value of the model parameters) and the observed behaviour of the system. Then, these techniques inherit all the difficulties present in (global) optimization problems, such as presence of several suboptimal solutions, ill conditioning of the (local) problem or difficulties with the convergence of some algorithms. But, in addition, parameter identification problems can exhibit an additional difficulty related to the lack of (practical) identifiability. Then, the observed response of the system used to measure the misfitting must be selected with care and not only optimization convergence results must be analyzed but identifiability and sensitivity analysis must be carried out as well [2], [7].

Effective identification techniques should then include both efficient combinations of global, local and hybrid optimization algorithms and good post-analysis tools. Practical parameter estimation can then greatly benefit from the availability of software packages implementing these techniques. One good example of such a tool is AMIGO2 software [1] developed by the Bioprocess Engineering Group at the Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas CSIC in Spain (<http://www.iim.csic.es/>).

In our problem, we consider $\omega(t)$ as the (only) system observable and wind velocity as the (only) system stimulation. Several identification problems concerning the SIMULINK model previously presented will be considered. In each of these problems some parts of the model will be assumed as unknown

Figure 11: Website homepage of AMIGO2 parameter identification software: <https://sites.google.com/site/amigo2toolbox/>

and (practical) identifiability as well as convergence of identification algorithms will be analyzed.

More precisely, two kinds of identification problems will be considered here. In one case it is assumed that enough information of the wind turbine is available in order to build a model so that only control parameters are to be identified. In the second case instead it is assumed that some information on the wind turbine can be missing and the corresponding identification problem would include wind turbine parameters as well.

8. On parameters identifiability

Some remarks concerning control and model parameters identifiability are in order. Firstly, control algorithm in the simplified SIMULINK model includes three parameters: PI control parameters K_P and K_I , and low-pass filter cut-off frequency ω_c . One can not expect identifiability of this set of parameters. Quite likely, two PI controllers with different values of the low-pass filter cut-off frequency can exhibit a similar dynamics if the values of K_P and K_I are conveniently selected in each case.

This conjecture can be easily verified with a test. We assume that aerodynamic, mechanical and electric model parameters are completely known and only PI control parameters are to be identified. A reference solution is generated with the simplified SIMULINK model. Then, PI control parameters (K_P and K_I) as well as low-pass filter cut-off frequency ω_c are identified minimizing the integral square error. In the identification algorithm, (derivative free) local techniques starting from different initial guesses are used.

Table 1 shows results from K_P , K_I and ω_c identification (reference solution

	K_P	K_I	ω_c	Iterations	Error
Initial guess # 1	0.009148	0.50016	393.85	181	6.13×10^{-6}
Initial guess # 2	0.010278	0.50013	325.66	153	1.00×10^{-6}
Initial guess # 3	0.011277	0.49882	253.86	89	8.69×10^{-6}

 Table 1: Identified values for K_P , K_I and ω_c

	K_P	K_I	Iterations	Error
Initial guess # 3	0.010000	0.50000	45	2.37×10^{-15}

 Table 2: Identified values for K_P and K_I

was computed for $K_P = 0.01$, $K_I = 0.5$ and $\omega_c = 314.159s^{-1}$). Ill conditioning of the minimization problem is clear. In table 2 results for a second test where ω_c is fixed (only K_P and K_I need to be identified) are shown (only one local search is shown). As a consequence, it seems clear that additional information/requirements can be used to select the low-pass filter cut-off frequency ω_c in control.

The second question regards identifiability of (open loop) wind turbine parameters. In particular, the possibility to identify aerodynamics parameters from observations of the (closed loop) wind turbine dynamics is considered. In a second test, the same reference solution is considered, and (simultaneous) identification of some aerodynamic parameters and control K_P and K_I is faced. Concerning aerodynamic parameters, coefficients C_1 , C_5 and C_6 (see equation 2) are selected (as parameters to identify) since they have the greatest influence on the power coefficient c_p .

As in the first test, (derivative free) local techniques are used starting from different initial guesses. In all (three) cases, where correct values are perturbed up to a 40%, both PI control parameters and aerodynamic parameters are well identified, as shown in table 3.

Figure 12 shows, in the upper part, wind speed record used as an input in the (closed loop) wind turbine model. The bottom part represents the prescribed pitch angle evolution corresponding to the reference solution described above and the pitch angle evolution corresponding to the identified parameters using the initial guess #1. As clearly seen in the figure, the agreement is

	K_P	K_I	C_1	C_5	C_6
Initial guess # 1	0.0100	0.5000	0.5176	21.0000	0.0068
Initial guess # 2	0.0100	0.5000	0.5176	21.0000	0.0068
Initial guess # 3	0.0100	0.5000	0.5176	21.0000	0.0068

 Table 3: Identified values for K_P , K_I , C_1 , C_5 and C_6 .

excellent (error is as low as 1.8375×10^{-18}) as anticipated by results in table 3. Small differences between both curves are due to a different selection of sampled times in both plots.

Figure 12: Wind velocity (up) and pitch angle evolution (down)

9. Conclusion

Starting from the industrial problem proposed by the company *Solute*, concerning the identification of a wind turbine control design able to produce some prescribed dynamics, a simplified version of this problem has been derived. This simplified problem retains all the essential ingredients of the industrial problem providing, at the same time, a suitable workbench to easily test different algorithms and ideas.

In order to deal with the simplified problem three tools are needed:

- a detailed wind turbine modelling tool,
- a flexible modelling tool able to interact with other software components, and
- a model identification toolbox rich enough to test different identification approaches.

The Study Group selected three software tools fitted to the above mentioned needs: OpenFAST ([5],[6]), SIMULINK and AMIGO2 ([1],[2]).

At the same time, a study case has been proposed. Given the detailed information available for this reference wind turbine, the 5MW NREL wind turbine ([4]) has been selected.

Using the above described software toolchain and the reference wind turbine, a complete workbench has been implemented.

Finally, a preliminary identifiability analysis has been carried out. From this analysis, it can be concluded that some degree of freedom concerning the selection of the low-pass filter cut-off frequency is possible (so that another design requirements could be also met). At the same time, this analysis reveals that some open-loop wind turbine parameters (concerning aerodynamical, mechanical or electrical properties) can also be efficiently identified using this approach.

As a consequence, both the development of a suitable workbench software toolchain and a few identification guidelines have been achieved in the Study Group. These results provide all the ingredients needed to test efficient identification algorithms to be later applied to the (computationally expensive) industrial problem. This is already starting to be done by the company.

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